

National multi-actor workshop to valorise the benefits of legume crops in legume value chains – research protocol

Alison Karley, Pietro Iannetta, Fanny Tran (JHI), Anissa C. Davel, Elisabete Pinto, Carla S. Santos, Marta W. Vasconcelos (UCP), Peter Roebing (UAVR), Anne Schneider (TI), Eva Bräuner Sørensen, Marian Damsgaard Thorsted, Jon Birger Pederson (SEGES), Pietro Goglio (UNIPG), Abbigel Sadhu, Sergiy Smetana (DIL), Richard Omari (ZALF), Benjamin Bodirsky (PIK), Vanessa Fuchs (AWI), Sasa Straus, Tamara Kozic (ITC), Zsofia Veer (AgKu), Orsolya Lazanyi, Agnes Neulinger (ESSRG), Eleonora Barilli (SOL), Elisa Pizarro Carbonell (APRI), Claudia Meier, Matthias Klaiss, Fatma Fevzi (FIBL), Thomas Nemecek (Agroscope), Tanja Popovska (AGFT), Nilar Win, Thomas Wilkinson (ADAS).

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Executive Summary

A protocol was prepared by the legumES project to assist partners in conducting ‘multi-actor workshops’ in their region. The aim of the workshops was to work with stakeholders and agrifood system actors to understand how the ecosystem services and benefits of legume crops and crop products might be valorised to promote their production and consumption. The protocol was co-developed and refined with project beneficiaries through a series of co-design and training workshops. This report provides the final version of the protocol that was applied in workshops held in 11 partner countries of the project.

Background

Legumes are an important part of a healthy diet and healthy environment, but legume cropping and levels of consumption are still very low in Europe. Previous research (e.g. [TRUE project](#)) has identified the practical barriers to uptake of legume cropping and legume consumption. The LegumES project seeks to overcome some of these barriers by understanding how legumes can support ecosystem services and other benefits in agri-food systems. The multi-actor workshop will ask legume stakeholders the question: What do you perceive to be the important benefits of legumes in agriculture and diets and how can we increase the value of these benefits in agri-food systems and society?

Here, ‘ecosystem services’ (ES) and Ecosystem Service benefits (ESb) refer to direct and indirect benefits provided to humans by the natural environment through specific ecosystem attributes, functions or processes. Such benefits include:

- **Provisioning Services**, i.e., the products obtained from ecosystems such as harvested fruits and grain for food, feed, or fuel;
- **Regulating & Supporting Services**, i.e., ecosystem processes such as carbon sequestration, pollination or supporting biodiversity; and,
- **Cultural Services**, i.e., non-material benefits people obtain from ecosystems, for example from being part of traditional farming practices or culinary traditions.

By working with stakeholders to co-create knowledge about the ecosystem benefits of legume production and consumption, the study will understand how legumes could be integrated into national agri-food systems through existing or novel schemes, interventions or incentives. This knowledge will be shared between the partner countries across Europe through the LegumES partnership. Further, the knowledge generated provides an important underpinning for follow-on activities in the project, both scientific and participatory research, to quantify the social, economic and environmental benefits of legumes.

To "valorise" is to recognize or create value in something. Definitions of valorise (Cambridge English Dictionary):

- To think or state that something has value or is valuable
- To make something valuable or useful from an existing substance

- To decide or increase the price or value of goods, services etc., for example by government action

This could mean thinking or declaring that something is valuable, like highlighting the importance of a historical site. It could also mean transforming something into something useful or valuable, like turning waste materials into new products. And sometimes, it involves setting or raising the value of goods or services, although valorising does not only relate to economic value. It includes anything that enhances significance, utility, or meaning. For example, valorisation can be:

- **Acknowledging** that something has inherent value (like cultural heritage).
- **Transforming** an existing material or idea into something useful or valued (like recycling waste into reusable materials).
- **Enhancing value** in a way that might be meaningful socially or environmentally, even if it doesn't have immediate financial benefits.

When we talk about valorising Ecosystem Services (ES) and Ecosystem Service benefits (ESb) provided by legumes, we are looking into how to **improve and increase the positive perception** of what legumes give in terms of their ecosystem services and benefits in order to increase adoption across the supply chain and in so doing increase their service provision. For example, bringing more awareness to the fact that certain legumes were part of traditional diets (e.g. by showcasing old recipes) could be a form of valorising a spiritual and cultural ecosystem services; here, the valorising is in terms of using education to acknowledge and increase awareness of cultural significance.

Methodology

1.1. Purpose

The aim of the workshop is to build **co-operative communities for home-grown legume production and consumption** to guide the development of living labs and other project activities.

Workshop question – the problem being addressed:

Legumes are an important part of a healthy diet and healthy environment, but legume cropping and levels of consumption are still very low in Europe.

*What do you think are **the important benefits of legumes** in agriculture and diets and **how can we increase their value** in agri-food systems and society?*

The objectives are:

- Prioritize stakeholders' goals** for legume production, and legume-associated ES valorisation
- Conceive future scenarios for legume use that optimise **opportunities for increased ES valorisation**
- Bring together key/influential stakeholders** to guide the Theory of Change approach and help develop project legacy

1.1.1. Participants

Target participants are **stakeholders involved in farming, supply chains, processing, end use, consumption** of legumes and other crops. It includes those not yet involved but might become more involved (e.g. farmers not yet growing legumes).

Participants will be invited to take part via a call for participants through the partner organisations' social media handles, newsletters, and emails to contacts where there are existing relationships, providing the project information sheet. The partners' previous work on legumes has led to them having a comprehensive network of stakeholders involved in legume production and consumption. They will invite their existing contacts to participate in this new initiative.

The benefits for the participants will be in contributing to understanding of how barriers to the production and consumption of legumes can be overcome in their country/region, and in Europe, by identifying priorities for valorising ecosystem benefits and mechanisms for implementing these through research, advice, and policy design.

Ideas for making the workshop attractive to participants:

- Combine the workshop with a field learning experience
- Invite someone along to the workshop that they would be interested to talk to
- Emphasise the workshop elements that allow people to talk to each other (including farmers talking to policy people who they would not usually get a chance to speak to)
- If budget allows, then reimburse travel costs
- Ask participants what they need from research (write on a poster before they leave)
- Highlight the opportunity to gain early insights into project results
- Consider if there is a national conversation that is relevant to the workshops that could allow stakeholders to provide comment/feedback, express opinions and providing a platform for discussion.

1.1.2. Ethics, GDPR, and health and safety considerations

Informed consent should be obtained from workshop participants prior to taking part in the workshop (see: [Appendix 1](#), which should be adapted to your country). The consent form includes a GDPR statement, and explains how confidential information will be treated, and participants' rights to withdraw.

The consent form is accompanied by a participant information sheet explaining the purpose of the workshop, the activities it involves, and how the workshop outputs will be used (see: [Appendix 2](#), which should be adapted to your country).

The research does not collect sensitive personal data. Raw data will be shared only among project staff within an organisation. All collected information should be anonymised before it is shared with project partners or disseminated to other audiences in project outputs.

Any non-anonymised information (e.g. contact list, consent forms) should be stored securely on network drive folders that can only be accessed by local project team members, using password-protection on files that are shared electronically (e.g. via email).

Data should be stored for a maximum of five years after the completion of the study, after which it should be deleted.

At the start of the workshop, ask participants to avoid making public any personally identifiable information of the other participants and not quote participants outside the workshop. This is to respect the right of participants to anonymity.

Please respond to any specific health and safety requests of participants (e.g. dietary allergies, accessibility needs), and ensure that fire alarm procedures are made known to the participants before the workshop starts. There could be risks of spread of COVID, so for that reason work is conducted in a well-ventilated room and ensuring social distancing when needed.

1.2. Workshop activities

An example of a workshop outline is given below, but other structures are possible. Choose the method you think will work best for your participants. The icebreaker can be refreshments/lunch or a specific activity.

Along with the consent form and information sheet (see above), a pre-event questionnaire is supplied to participants (see: [Appendix 3](#), which should be translated into the local language) asking about their perceptions of **the benefits (social, economic, environmental) of legumes** and **which ones they prioritise**. The questionnaire can be sent to participants as an email attachment or provided as an anonymised online form. If preferred, it can be completed at the start of the workshop. Results from the questionnaire indicates the depth of explanation needed in the workshop about ES/ESb and can be used as prompts in the workshop activities.

Output 1a: spreadsheet of scored ES/ESb allowing us to understand what participants understand about legume benefits/ecosystem services.

1.2.1. Step 1: Welcome

- Introduce the project and its main aims, and the facilitators, delegates
- Explain the aims and method of the workshop, go through the timetable of activities
 - Describe and define Ecosystem Services (ES) / Ecosystem Service benefits (ESb)
 - Please spend time explaining that the workshop activities are focussed on **valorising the benefits from legumes**. We are not asking participants to valorise legumes *per se* as crops/food etc. (this has been done several times already in previous projects). Give examples at each step of the workshop (see table with suggestions further below)

- List the expected outputs and follow-on communication (of outputs/findings)
- Give participants the opportunity to ask questions and clarifications
- It can be helpful to show how the workshop activities will proceed using a visual illustration on a slide (see examples below)

Figure 1. Example arrangement of groups and timings for the prioritisation of legume ecosystem services and benefits (workshop organised by DIL).

Figure 2. Example arrangement of groups and timings for the SWOT analysis of valorising legume ecosystem services and benefits (workshop organised by DIL).

1.2.2. Step 2: Ecosystem function prioritisation

This could be conducted using a ‘World Café’ approach, but other methods can be used.

- Divide the ES/ESb into environmental, socio-cultural, economic services/benefits (see the spreadsheet template for guidance)
- Place a list of each category (3 categories in total) on each café table
- Divide participants into groups and assign each group to one table
- no more than 5 participants per table (plus facilitator)
- duplicate tables for each ES/ESb category (as there will be >25 participants)
- Ask participants to discuss the list of ES/ESb and add any more that come to mind
- Ask participants to vote for their priority ES/ESb using dot stickers (up to three priorities per person)
- Move participants to another table, refreshing the list on each table
- Photograph the ES/ESb sheets scored by participants

Output1b: Expanded spreadsheet (output 1a) of environmental, social-cultural, economic services/benefits ranked by stakeholder priorities.

1.2.3. Step 3: SWOT analysis

This could be conducted using a carousel method to answer the question ‘In your country or region, what are the strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats to **valorising the ecosystem benefits of legume production/consumption systems?**’

Remember that valorising (i.e. ascribing value) to ecosystem services and benefits does not only relate to their economic value. See Table 1 for some examples.

- Set up four posters labelled ‘Strengths’ ‘Weakness’ ‘Opportunities’ ‘Threats’
- Explain what each SWOT category means
- Divide participants into two groups and assign to strengths or weaknesses
- Ask participants to consider the **strengths and weaknesses of valorising ecosystem benefits** associated with legume production/consumption. Provide an example of what this means*. They should write these onto sticky notes and place on the poster board, then swap to the opposite board.
- Ask participants to write in complete sentences on post-it notes – to make translation easier.
- Repeat the process for opportunities and threats, asking participants to identify **opportunities for, and threats to, valorising the ecosystem benefits** of legume production/consumption. Provide an example of what this means*.

- Photograph each group’s SWOT posters

Table 1. *SWOT examples. Feel free to use, adapt or create your own examples. These examples are designed to help facilitators elicit responses from participants. Please try to avoid giving all these examples to participants, as it might influence their contributions to this exercise. The important thing is to identify SWOTs of **valorising** ES/ESb of legumes (and avoid going down the path of valorising legume cropping, as this has already been done by several research projects).

SWOT category	Ask participants to think about...	Examples
Strength	Does valorising legume-based ecosystem services/benefits strengthen crop production and food systems?	<p>Valorising legume ES/ES benefits can:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • reward farmers for reducing their environmental footprint (e.g. less N fertiliser needed) • raise the profile of legume products to consumers • recognise the cultural importance of traditional legume crops and foods
Weakness	Does valorising legume-based ecosystem services/benefits weaken crop production, and downstream value chains?	<p>Valorising legumes ES/ES benefits might:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • increase the price of legume products, making them less competitive with other protein sources (e.g. meat) • increase the burden on farmers to provide evidence of ES/ESb..and.. • not be consistently supported by evidence due to variable crop performance • not be enough to overcome the limited appeal of legume-based products to consumers (taste, texture, ‘poverty’ protein source etc.).
Opportunity	Could valorising ecosystem services/benefits of legumes create, for example, new jobs, new sources of income, better standard of living or health, a better environment?	<p>Valorising legume ES/ES benefits could:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • form the basis of a marketing strategy for (new) legume products (e.g. based on environmental conscience, climate action etc.) • encourage the collection of data needed to evidence the requirements for farm payments (carbon, biodiversity, climate etc.)
Threat	What might happen to prevent the valorisation of legume-based	<p>Valorising legume ES/ES benefits might:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • be undermined by national regulations that place limits on legume cropping area or

	ecosystem services/benefits from being achieved?	<p>frequency (e.g. for pest/disease management)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • meet consumer resistance due to entrenched diet/eating habits • fail to encourage market expansion for legume products due to costs of living constraints on household budgets
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Output 2: SWOT analysis of the strengths/weaknesses and opportunities/threats of valorising the ES/ESb of current legume production/consumption systems in your region/country. Also provides an initial exploration of requirements for Living Labs in each region/country.

1.2.4. Step 4: Drivers of change

This activity is only carried out if time allows.

- Set up five new poster sheets each labelled with one of the STEEP headings
- Split the participants into two groups (opportunities, threats) and ask each group of participants to examine the sticky notes posted onto the ‘Opportunities’ and ‘Threats’ posters; first mark them as O or T and then categorise them into one of the five STEEP categories (example below)

TECHNOLOGY	ENVIRONMENT	POLICY	ECONOMIC	SOCIETY
<p><i>Alternative fertilisers or pesticides</i></p> <p><i>Technology to recycle nutrients from wastewater</i></p> <p><i>New, more efficient cropping practices</i></p> <p><i>Alternative crops</i></p>	<p><i>Extreme weather events affect crop growth</i></p> <p><i>Warmer climate allows new crops to be grown</i></p>	<p><i>Regulation to limit fertiliser or pesticide use</i></p> <p><i>Incentives to use alternatives to fertilisers and pesticides</i></p> <p><i>Net Zero goals</i></p>	<p><i>Cost of fertilizers/pesticides</i></p> <p><i>Cost of energy and fuel.</i></p> <p><i>Cost/income from low N crop products (pulses).</i></p>	<p><i>Consumer habits - fruit and vegetables, especially legumes - meat/dairy</i></p> <p><i>Use of crops to feed humans rather than animals</i></p>

- Split participants into five groups, one per STEEP category. Ask participants to discuss amongst themselves which drivers have most impact (and which drivers are most uncertain to happen in the future)
- Ask participants to vote individually for the most impactful and most uncertain drivers in each category (use dot voting, with different colour dots for impact and uncertainty); one vote per category for impact and one vote per category for uncertainty

Output 3: ranking of most influential drivers of legume ES/ESb and most uncertain drivers

The drivers with greatest impact AND most uncertainty (=critical uncertainties) can be used to construct future scenarios.

1.2.5. Step 5: Summary and next steps

- Explain how the outputs of each part of the workshop will be used and the likely timeline
- **Offer participants the opportunity to remain involved in project activities** (including scenario creation and pilot studies/living labs), and keep your own records of stakeholders wishing to remain involved
- **Offer participants the opportunity to ask questions and provide feedback** on the workshop, noting these in your workshop report.

Output 4: Communities of practice for legume production initiated or consolidated (country or regional level), comprising actors in farming, processing, consumption, regulation, willing to remain engaged with the project and beyond

Data collection and validation instruments

Signed consent forms should be scanned and stored in a secure folder (only accessible by the workshop organisers) either on your own institutional IT network or as a secure subfolder in the relevant folder for your multi-actor workshop on the internal LegumES SharePoint site.

Data collected from the pre-event survey and workshop activities will be tabulated in an excel file and presented in a workshop report.

The methods described here have been used previously by participants in past projects. See examples here:

SWOT analysis: The strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats presented by a transition from a conventional farming model to a more agroecological model were assessed by farmers and other people involved in agriculture:

<https://www.climatechange.org.uk/projects/the-potential-for-an-agroecological-approach-in-scotland-policy-brief/>

Drivers of change assessed as part of a future scenario planning exercise: <https://www.epicscotland.org/resources/scenario-planning-as-communicative-action-lessons-from-participatory-exercises-conducted-for-the-scottish-livestock-industry/>

Workshop materials

- Sign in sheet and tick box for newsletter
- Convert questionnaire into online survey
- Printed consent forms
- Pull-up banner
- Name badges, list of names for registering on arrival
- Introductory slides to the project and the workshop activities
- Printed out list of ES/ESb, one per category, with blank rows for adding more to the lists
- Coloured stickers for voting (four colours, one per stakeholder type)
- Flip chart paper and pens and blutak
- Post-it notes (different colours)
- Summing up slides
- Newsletter / flyer to hand out

Disclaimer

Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union, UK Research, and Innovation (UKRI), European Research Executive Agency (REA) or Swiss State Secretariat for Education, Research, and Innovation (SERI). Neither the European Union nor any other granting authority can be held responsible for them.

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Appendix 1 – Consent Form

How can we increase the value of legume ecosystem benefits in [insert country name] agri-food systems?

RESEARCH CONSENT FORM

This consent form relates to a stakeholder workshop and related pre-workshop survey and post-workshop report. The objective of this workshop is to bring together stakeholders to better understand the important benefits of legumes and how their value could be increased in agri-food systems and society. You are being invited to participate in this study because of your expertise and experience within the [insert country name] agri-food system. You are welcome to ask for further information about the project by emailing the contact persons at the bottom of the page.

Participant Identification Number:

Title of Project:	Valorising the ecosystem benefits of legumes in [insert country name] agri-food systems.
Principal Investigator(s):	Insert names of researchers carrying out the workshop
Study Number:	LegumES-01

Place Initials in the Box

I confirm that I have read, or had read to me, and understand the information sheet for the above study. I have had the opportunity to ask questions, and these have been answered fully and explicitly.	
I understand that my participation is voluntary, and I am free to withdraw at any time, during the workshop, without providing any reason and without my legal rights being affected, and that I will not be able to withdraw my contributions made in the workshop that are no longer identifiable as mine.	
I understand the study is being conducted by researchers from [insert lead partner name], at the request of the European Commission for the project 'LegumES'. This is expected to end in December 2027.	
I understand the findings will be disseminated to policy, regulatory, industry and science groups.	
I understand that confidentiality will be maintained by the research team, and it will not be possible to be identified from any publications/outputs resulting from this study.	
I understand my identity and the data I contribute during the workshop (e.g. my shared views) will be disclosed to other workshop participants.	
I agree to take part in the above study.	
I agree for the discussions to be recorded.	
I agree to being contacted at a later date in relation to this research/ study.	

I agree to not disclose other participants identity and their views outside of the workshop	
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Name of Participant (please print)	Signature	Date
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PI/Researcher Name (please print)	Signature	Date
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Privacy Notice

The [\[insert lead partner name\]](#) ("[\[insert partner abbreviation\]](#)", "us" or "we") will use your personal data for the purposes of the research undertaken in the project '**LegumES' - Valorisation of ecosystem services provided by legume crops**). **Task 1.1: Analysis with stakeholders of barriers and opportunities for regional legume value chains** in accordance with our privacy notice at [\[insert weblink to lead partner privacy statement\]](#).

We are the data controller for the personal data which we hold about you for the purposes of this project. We are committed to protecting your privacy and will process your personal data in accordance with the [\[insert country name\] General Data Protection Regulation](#) ([\[insert country law number\]](#)) and the European Data Protection Act 2018 (DPA).

Our main privacy notice will explain what we do with personal data in more detail as well as your rights. Or, if you have any queries about your personal data, you can contact our Data Protection Officer on [\[insert email address of lead partner DPO\]](#).

For further information, including independent data protection advice and information in relation to your rights, you can contact the information Commissioner at: [\[insert address, telephone number of country contact\]](#), Website: [\[insert website\]](#). You can also report any concerns here: [\[insert weblink for reporting data breaches in your country\]](#)

For more information about the project please contact any of the researchers below.

[\[insert name of partner contact email address institution\]](#)

Telephone: [\[insert telephone number\]](#)

Appendix 2 - Information Sheet

How can we increase the value of legume ecosystem benefits in [insert country name] agri-food systems.

About this research.

Legumes are an important part of a healthy diet and healthy environment, but legume cropping and levels of consumption are still very low in Europe. This research is about consulting stakeholders involved in agri-food systems to find out what they consider to be the important benefits of legumes and how their value could be increased in agri-food systems and society.

The project is carried out by [insert researcher names], scientists at [insert partner organisation name]. The project receives funding from the European Union’s Horizon Europe programme.

Why should I participate?

Your participation is very valuable for this research. This research will help with understanding which benefits of legumes, whether environmental, economic or societal, are most valued by people involved in agri-food systems. The information you provide will be used to determine how legume benefits can be prioritised for monitoring and valorisation in current and future agri-food systems. The results will be communicated widely to inform work in policy, agri-food industries and research.

Research Approach.

This research consists of a one-day workshop. A short (10 minute) survey will be supplied prior to attending the workshop to gather your preliminary ideas of legume benefits, and afterwards you will have the opportunity to provide feedback on the workshop results (the report will be shared by email). The workshop timetable and activities are shown below.

10 am	Welcome: introduce the workshop aims and activities, and answer questions
10.30 am	Refreshment break
11 am	Activity 1: identify benefits of legumes through discussion and using interactive visual aids; and prioritise these benefits
12 pm	Lunch
1 pm	Activity 2: assess Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities and Threats of valorising legume benefits through discussion and using interactive poster boards
2.30 pm	Refreshment break
3 pm	Activity 3: Identify the Opportunities and Threats that could have most impact or that are most uncertain to happen through discussion and participant ranking

4 pm	Summary and next steps: Explain how the workshop results will be used and the timeline, and opportunities for further involvement
4.30 pm	Event close

Data analysis and confidentiality: what will happen to the data I provide?

All data you provide will be treated as confidential. You will not be identifiable within any research publications and outputs resulting from this research study. Only [\[insert partner organisation name\] researchers](#) will have access to raw data. It will not be shared and to avoid unintended disclosure, personal data will be imported to a password-protected excel file, stored on a secure network server.

Anonymised data will be reported in the outputs of this project. Your personal data will not be shared at any time. All responses will be anonymised and nothing in the research outputs will make you identifiable. We will keep the anonymised data for 5 years. When published, the anonymised dataset will be assigned a licence that maximises accessibility and re-use, as required by the funder.

Do I have to take part?

Your participation is voluntary, and you can withdraw at any time. If you would like to withdraw, please contact [\[insert email address of lead researcher\]](#). The data you provide will be withdrawn before analysis, but once anonymised and/or published it cannot be withdrawn.

There are no incentives for participating in this research. We will reimburse travel costs incurred by attending the workshop and we will provide refreshments and food.

Are there any possible risks from taking part? There are no risks from taking part in this research as any confidential information will be anonymised.

Further questions and who to contact.

If you have any questions, please do not hesitate to contact us:
[\[insert lead researcher name and email address\]](#)

For further information, including independent data protection advice and information in relation to your rights, you can contact the information Commissioner at the [\[insert country name\] Data Protection Authority](#)

[\[insert name of country DPA\]](#)

Address

Telephone number

Website]

You can also report any concerns here: [\[insert country weblink for reporting data breaches\]](#)

Appendix 3 – Pre-event questionnaire

Questions:

1. Country (scroll down and click)
2. Region (scroll down and click)
3. Farmer, researcher, advisor, industry, other (choose one perspective)
4. Which legume crops are grown in your country/region for
 - Food:
 - Feed:
 - Fibre:
 - Fuel:

Legumes include crops grown for fresh green pods or grain, or dried grain (faba/field beans, peas, soybean, lupin, chickpea, lentil, common beans, cowpea, grass pea, etc.), as cover/forage crops (vetch, clovers, lucerne, etc.). Also, species of semi-natural systems including woody species (such as gorse, and broom), and other wild legumes (e.g., *Astragalus*, *Oxytropis*).

5. In your experience, how do stakeholders value the impact of legumes on the following:
[using a rating scale: benefit, disbenefit, neutral, or variable outcome, allow respondents to select all that apply in the list below]

Provisioning

- Yield
- Yield stability
- Crop product quality
- Food production
- Feed production (Livestock including poultry, Aquaculture)
- Profitability
- Diversifying income
- Wild foods
- Allow other options to be added and scored by the respondent

Regulating and supporting

- Air quality
- Water quality
- Carbon sequestration
- Pest and pathogen control
- Biodiversity support
- Pollination
- Soil formation and maintenance
- Soil fertility
- Nutrient cycling

- Soil structure and erosion control
- Allow other options to be added and scored by the respondent

Cultural

- Recreation and ecotourism
 - Ethical and/or traditional culture values

 - Allow other options to be added and scored by the respondent
 - Please explain your selections [free text]
6. Which of these legume benefits are most important to quantify and how would you recommend their value is recognised? (e.g. through product labelling, environmental incentive schemes, or other means) [free text response]